

Cognitive Approaches to Metaphor in Political and Paremiological Contexts

Qodirova Maftuna Davron qizi

EFL teacher, UzSWLU, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

missdove93@gmail.com

Abstract

At present Metaphor is the centre of attention of modern linguists. The theory of metaphor has undergone a lot of changes with the development of cognitive linguistics. There appeared a new cognitive approach to metaphor. According to this Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) metaphor is not a stylistic device but a way of thinking and cognition. The main purpose of the paper is investigating the cognitive and cultural aspects of metaphor. It is achieved by comparative and qualitative research methods. This process includes studying the conceptual metaphor theory and classification, analyzing some examples and specific features of them in different text types like in the field of politics and in paremiology. Based on some results this article presents some linguistic analysis of metaphors which are found commonly in political discourse and leader's speeches. These findings can serve for further researches on metaphor in language, thought and culture.

Keywords: metaphor, comparative method, qualitative method, political discourse, paremiology

Аннотация

В настоящее время метафора находится в центре внимания современных лингвистов. Теория метафоры претерпела множество изменений с развитием когнитивной лингвистики. Появился новый когнитивный подход к метафоре. Согласно этой концептуальной теории метафоры (КТМ) метафора является не стилистическим приемом, а способом мышления и познания. Основная цель статьи - исследование когнитивных и культурных аспектов метафоры. Это достигается сравнительными и качественными методами исследования. Этот процесс включает изучение теории и классификации концептуальных метафор, анализ некоторых примеров и их особенностей в различных типах текстов, как в области политики, так и в паремиологии. На основе некоторых результатов в этой статье представлен лингвистический анализ метафор, которые обычно встречаются в политическом дискурсе и речах лидеров. Эти выводы могут послужить для дальнейших исследований метафоры в языке, мышлении и культуре.

Ключевые слова: метафора, сравнительный метод, качественный метод, политический дискурс, паремиология.

Annotatsiya

Hozirgi vaqtda metafora zamonaviy tilshunoslarning diqqat markazida. Kognitiv tilshunoslikning rivojlanishi bilan metafora nazariyasi juda ko'p o'zgarishlarga duch keldi. Metaforaga yangi kognitiv yondashuv paydo bo'ldi. Ushbu kontseptual metafora nazariyasiga (CMT) ko'ra, metafora stilistik vosita emas, balki fikrlash va bilish usulidir. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi metaforaning kognitiv va madaniy jihatlarini o'rganishdir. Bunga qiyosiy va sifatli tadqiqot usullari orqali erishiladi. Bu jarayon kontseptual metafora nazariyasini va tasnifini o'rganishni, ba'zi misollar va ularning turli matn turlarida, masalan, siyosat va paremiologiyada o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ba'zi natijalarga asoslanib, ushbu maqolada siyosiy nutq va rahbar nutqlarida tez-tez uchraydigan metaforalarning ba'zi lingvistik tahlillari keltirilgan. Ushbu topilmalar til, tafakkur va madaniyatdagi metafora bo'yicha keyingi tadqiqotlar uchun xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Tayanch iboralar: metafora, qiyosiy metod, sifat metodi, siyosiy nutq, paremiologiya

Introduction

Metaphor, a significant branch of linguistics has aroused so much interest to scholars since the ancient times. There appeared different views in the study of metaphor. Mainly traditional and modern approaches which interpret metaphor in the line of rhetorics and cognition have come into being. Initially, Aristotle discussed the traditional metaphor in his works: *Poetics* and *Rhetorics*. In *Poetics* Aristotle gives his definition of metaphor: "Metaphor consists in giving the thing a name that belongs to something else; the transference being either from genus to species, or from species to genus, or from species to species, or on grounds of analogy" (Lan,2005). Paul Ricoeur, the twentieth-century philosopher exposed the creative aspect of language in his theory of metaphor. Ricoeur (1978) described that the metaphor is a special combination of words that as a clash of distant semantic fields forces the reader to interpret the sentence in a new way and see things in a new light. Studies of metaphor have taken on an absolutely new look ever since 1980s. "Metaphors We Live by" written by G. Lakoff and M. Johnson (1980) has rocked to the core studies of metaphor in linguistic field. This work suggests that metaphor is a matter of thought and action rather than a device of the rhetoric flourish. Kovecses (1986) affirms that feelings such as anger, pride and love are conceptualized structure in everyday language. This paper is devoted to reveal the cognitive and cultural aspects of metaphor with the examples in different text types. Analyzed examples and discussed items give the conclusion that metaphor is a way of our cognition and cognitive tool which can present particular cultural sign.

Methods

First of all, this research involves to explore the metaphor theory according to the traditional viewpoint. For example, many scholars created their theory by giving definition, classification and clarifying functions of metaphor. In this process the comparative method was used in order to distinguish the ideas of many scholars. The problem requires to study Conceptual Metaphor Theory and Lakoff's classification in its turn. Conceptual metaphor is understanding one domain of experience in terms of another. And Lakoff classifies the conceptual metaphors as follows: Structural, orientational, ontological and container metaphors. Then some metaphor examples are presented in different text types such as political and paremiological texts. In this case Qualitative method is used for data collection.

Results

The analysis of metaphor examples shows much results in the research. For instance, the peculiarities and aspects of metaphor are presented in political texts. In political discourse the use of conceptual metaphors has some specific features:

- **Figurehead:** a leader whose powers are entirely symbolic, such as a constitutional monarch. **(Relating to the executive)**
- **Sunset clause** to prevent legislation from being permanent. **(Relating to legislation)**
- **Paper candidate:** a candidate who puts no effort into his campaign and is essentially just a name on the ballot. **(Relating to the elections)**

Besides, in paremiology especially proverbs have a good relationship with metaphor. Majority of proverbs use metaphors and makes them extremely valuable linguistic tool. For example:

"No rose without thorn", "Ants united can carry a dead elephant to their abode"

Discussion

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Among other traditionally recognized figures of speech metaphor has attracted more scientists. For instance, Aristotle emphasizes the cognitive function of metaphors. In order to understand a metaphor, it is important to find something common between the metaphor and the thing the metaphor refers to. According to Galperin metaphors can be genuine and trite according to the degree of unexpectedness. Metaphors which are quite unexpected are called genuine metaphors. Sometimes trite metaphors are fixed in dictionaries as expressive means of language. Moreover, as well as tradition metaphor, modern metaphor theory has begun to develop. The authors of a new cognitive theory of metaphor are George Lakoff and Mark Johnson who wrote a famous book "Metaphors we live by". According to this theory, metaphor is defined as a cognitive process. A conceptual metaphor connects one idea to another one in order to understand something well. Conceptual metaphor is one of the fundamental processes of analogical thinking (Lakoff, 1980). According to the cognitive theory, conceptual metaphor consists of the interaction of two cognitive structures (domains): the target domain and the source domain. The target domain is described and is assimilated to source domain. For instance, "Mind is Machine". George Lakoff and Mark Johnson distinguished several types of conceptual metaphors in their work "Metaphors We Live By":

- Structural metaphor, which consists of structural organization of one abstract concept in terms of another concrete concept. (Time is Money)
- Orientational metaphor organizes a whole system of concepts with respect to one another. (Life is up. Death is down)
- Ontological metaphor, which concrete concept is projected onto abstract concept. (The Mind is Entity)
- Container metaphor. In this type one conceptual structure is supposed to be "IN" another conceptual structure. (He is in love).

Conclusion

From those we have discussed above it can be concluded that metaphor is more a means of cognizing the world than purely a literary device. Because we think metaphorically. Conceptual metaphor does not belong to the language only, it can be expressed both by verbal and non-verbal means. Our everyday lives are full of conceptual metaphors and sometimes we don't even notice them. Furthermore, it is well known to us that metaphor is the carrier of culture and reflects ways of cognizing the world. Thus, conceptual metaphor is more significant with a great role in studying the history, politics, culture and traditions.

References:

1. Chun, Lan. (2005). Cognitive Linguistics and Metaphoric Study. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research press.
2. I.R.Galperin, (1977). Stylistics. Moscow. p. 140.
3. Kovecses,G.(1986). Metaphors of Anger, Pride and Love. Amstendam:Benjamins
4. Lakoff, G. and Johnson, M. (1980). Metaphors We Live By. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
5. Lakoff, G. (1980). The Metaphorical Structure of the Human Conceptual System. University of California,Berkeley. SCIENCE 4, 195-208.
6. Ricoeur, Paul. (1978) The Metaphorical Process as Cognition, Imagination, and Feeling. *Critical Inquiry* 1, no. 5, 143–159.